

Paper 12

DIGITALIZATION IN EDUCATION - A COMPARATIVE STUDY BETWEEN GOVERNMENT SCHOOL TEACHERS AND PRIVATE SCHOOL TEACHERS IN MANGALURU CITY.

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Abstract :

Information technology has reformed each sector it has grasped and it is currently in the promising phases of altering academia. In the coming decades if information technology has its approach, education will be far changed, more immersive and hopefully more constructive to the people than it is today. Digitization in education industry has totally changed the learning and also the teaching process to a very great extent. Technology has made imparting education stress-free for both students and educators. The true revolution in education can only be achieved via digitization of education so that students can learn at their own speed both within and outside the classroom. Their learning upgrades while they carry on to advantage from fostering, mentorship and direction of their teachers. Various teachers are ready to accept the wave of digitization but more effort still need to be exercised when it comes to teacher training. Most educators are at the stage of figuring out how to use technology meaningfully for teaching. And these teachers are right to be concerned, since depending on how it is used, technology can either help or hinder the education process. So, this paper highlights the gap between the usage of digital technologies in teaching between the private school teachers and government school teachers and to know their perception regarding digitalization.

Keywords: Digitalisation, Teachers, Students, digital techniques.

1. INTRODUCTION

In the 21st century, so many of our old assumptions and ideas have turned around. It is clearly a different place in which the kids are growing up. More than 75% of the Indian population has a cell phone. A new online world has emerged and has become the focus of many of today's kid's attention. In such environment, that change would finally come to our young people's education as well, and it has.

Today's students do not have short attention spans or the inability to concentrate that they are often accused of having, many of the same students who do not concentrate in schools will sit focused on movies or video games. More and more young people are now deeply technology enhanced, connected to their peers and the world in ways no generation has ever been before.

Streams of information come at the 24*7. More and more of what they want and need is available in their pocket on demand.

All teachers today know that digital technology is becoming an important part of student's education. But just how to use it in schools is not yet completely clear, and most educators are at the stage of figuring out how to use technology meaningfully for teaching. And these teachers are right to be concerned, since depending on how it is use, technology can either help or hinder the educations process. So this paper highlights the gap between the usage of digital technologies in teaching between the private school teachers and government school teachers and to know their perception regarding digitalization.

2. OBJECTIVES

- To know the perception of teachers towards digitalisation in education.
- To know the adoptability of teachers towards digital education.
- To compare the perception and adoptability.

3. METHODOLOGY

For data collection, structured questions were framed and 16 questionnaires were filled through Google forms and 34 questionnaires were filled through personal interview method. The sample size was 50. The samples were the primary government school and private school teachers working in Mangaluru city. Quota sampling method is used to collect the primary data. Based on the requirements of the study data are also collected from various secondary sources such as internet, PDF files etc.

4. DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

The survey results are organized as follows. In the first section, the demographic profile of the respondents is presented. Where this section has been classified into categories and 25 respondents each from government schools and private schools is taken into consideration.

PROFILE OF RESPONDENTS: The selected 50 respondents include the primary government school and private school teachers working in Mangaluru city. A profile of respondents based on gender, age, sector, educational qualification and work experience are presented below.

Table 1: Gender wise distribution of sample

Gender	Government respondents	Percentage	Private respondents	Percentage
Male	-	-	-	-
Female	25	100	25	100
Total	25	100	25	100

Primary data

Table 2: Age wise distribution of the sample

Age	Govt respondents	Percentage	Pvt respondents	Percentage
18-30years	-	-	5	20
31-40years	4	16	10	40
41-50years	6	24	5	20
51 and above	15	60	5	20
Total	25	100	25	100

Primary Data

Table 3: Educational Qualification wise distribution of sample

Education qualification	Govt respondents	Percentage	Pvt respondents	Percentage
PUC	3	12	-	-
Graduate	5	20	09	36
Post Graduate	5	20	12	48
D.Ed	12	48	04	16
TOTAL	25	100	25	100

Primary Data

Table 4: Teaching experience of respondents

Experience	Govt respondents	Percentage	Pvt respondents	Percentage
Less than 5 years	1	4	07	28
5 – 15 years	1	4	08	32
15 – 25 years	13	52	06	24
25 & above	10	40	04	16
TOTAL	25	100	25	100

Primary Data

Above tables reveals the demographic profile of the respondents. On the basis of demographic profile following analysis and interpretations are made.

Table no 5: Response towards usage of modern methods in teaching

Particulars	Govt respondents	Percentage	Pvt respondents	Percentage
Yes	14	56	23	92
No	11	44	02	08
Total	25	100	25	100

Primary Data

The above table reveals the usage of modern methods in teaching. In the government school's majority 56% of them make use of modern techniques and only 44% of the respondents do not use modern techniques while teaching. In the private school's majority 92% of the teachers are inclined towards the modern teaching methods and only 08% of the respondent's do not use modern techniques. As compared to the government school's usage level is higher in the private schools.

Testing of hypothesis I

Response of government school and private school teachers towards usage of digital technology

Table 5. 11

Perception	Govt teachers	Private teachers	Total
Yes	14	23	37
No	11	2	13
Total	25	25	50

Primary Data

H0: No difference between the government and private school teachers in using digital technology

H1: There is difference between the government and private school teachers in using digital technology

Chi square test:

Row total for the row of that cell X Column total for the Column of that cell

$$\text{Expected frequency of any cell} = \frac{\text{Row total for the row of that cell} \times \text{Column total for the Column of that cell}}{\text{Grand total}}$$

Table 5.12 Expected frequencies or Expected values

Perception	Govt teachers	Private teachers	Total
Yes	18.5	18.5	37
No	6.5	6.5	13
Total	25	25	50

Primary Data

Table 5.13: Calculation of Chi square

Observed frequency	Expected frequency	(O-E) ² /E
14	18.5	1.095
11	6.5	3.115
23	18.5	1.095
02	6.5	3.115
		8.42

Primary Data

$$X^2 = \sum [(O-E)^2/E] = 8.42$$

$$V = (r-1)(c-1) = (2-1)(2-1) = 1$$

For V = 1: Table value of Chi square at 5% level of significance = 3.841

Since the calculated value of Chi square is more than the Table value of Chi square, the null hypothesis is rejected and alternative hypothesis is accepted. **We therefore conclude that there is significance difference between the government and private school teachers in using digital technology.**

Table no 5.21: Response towards techniques of modern teaching

Particulars	Govt respondents	Percentage	Pvt respondents	Percentage
Smart class	3	20	18	50
PPT	2	13.33	11	30.5
WhatsApp learning	-	-	-	-
Others	10	66.67	7	19.5
Total	15	100	36	100

*Multiple responses

Primary Data

The above table reveals the response towards modern techniques. In government schools 66.67% respondents make use of tabs, mobile phones, laptops while teaching and the least preferred method is ppt that is 13.33%. In private school's majority 50% of the teachers make use of smart classes as compared to the other techniques.

Table no 5.22: Response towards span of usage

Particulars	Govt respondents	Percentage	Pvt respondents	Percentage
Less than 1 year	5	35.71	4	17.39
2-4 years	8	57.14	9	39.13
4-6 years	1	7.14	5	21.74
6 years and above	-	-	5	21.74
Total	14	100	23	100

Primary Data

The above table reveals the span of using digital technology. In the government schools Majority 57.14% of the teachers use the digital teaching methods for more than 2 years and less than 4 years. Similarly, in private school's also majority 39.13% of the respondents use the digital technology for more than 2 years. When compared to government schools, private schools have an experience of using digital methods for a longer period.

Table no 5.23: Response towards impact of digitalization on workload

Particulars	Govt respondents	Percentage	Pvt respondents	Percentage
Yes	2	14.29	11	47.83
No	12	85.71	12	52.17
Total	14	100	23	100

Primary Data

The above table reveals that in the government school's majority 85.71% of the respondents feel that there is no impact on their work due to digitalization and for the remaining 14.29% it has impacted their work. Similarly, in the private schools Majority 52.17% of the respondents have no impact on their work due to implementation of digital education.

Particulars	Govt respondents	Percentage	Pvt respondents	Percentage
Yes	6	42.86	16	69.57
No	8	57.14	7	30.43
Total	14	100	23	100

Table no 5.24: Response towards compulsion in using digitalization

Primary Data

The above table reveals that in 57.14% of the government schools it is not mandatory to use digital techniques whereas 69.57% of the private schools make digitalization mandatory. This shows that private schools give more importance to e-learning.

Table no 5.31: Response towards reasons for not adopting digitalization

Particulars	Govt respondents	Percentage	Pvt respondents	Percentage
Lack of knowledge	4	21.05	-	-
Lack of infrastructure	4	21.05	-	-
Lack of time	-	-	1	33.33
Not mandatory	11	57.9	2	66.67
Total	19	100	3	100

***Multiple responses**

Primary Data

The above table reveals that, in government school's majority 57.9% of the teachers do not use digitalization as it is not mandatory and 21.05% of the respondents do not make use of digitalization due to lack of knowledge and infrastructure respectively. Similarly, out of 3 private school responses majority 66.67% of them have restricted to traditional methods of teaching and 33.33% of the respondent do not make use of digitalization due to lack of time.

Particulars	Govt respondents	Percentage	Pvt respondents	Percentage
Yes	2	8	22	88
No	23	92	3	12
Total	25	100	25	100

Table no 6: Response towards training to teachers in using digital techniques

Primary Data

The above table reveals that in government school's majority 92% of teachers have not got any training to use the digital techniques and in contrast majority 88% of the private school teachers have got the training for using digital techniques. As in government school's no much importance is given for the training of the teachers because there is no compulsion in using digital techniques.

Particulars	Govt respondents	Percentage	Pvt respondents	Percentage
Yes	11	44	25	100
No	14	56	-	-
Total	25	100	25	100

Table no 7: Responses towards computer education as a part of curriculum

Primary Data

The above table reveals that 56% of government schools respondents do not have computer classes and only 44% of the respondent's schools provide computer education. where as 100% of private school's respondents have computer classes as a part of curriculum. As basic computer knowledge is necessary for today's competitive world and all private schools knowing its importance have implemented it their curriculum as compared to government schools.

Particulars	Govt respondents	Percentage	Pvt respondents	Percentage
Yes	22	88	24	96
No	3	12	1	4
Total	25	100	25	100

Table no 8: Responses towards updating parents on student's status

Primary Data

The above table reveals the Response towards updating parents on student's status. In government school's majority 88% of the teachers update on student's status and only 12% of them do not update on student's status. In private schools' majority 96% of the teachers update parents on student's status whereas only 4% teachers do not update on student's status.

Table no 8.1: Response towards the techniques of updating the parents on student's status

Particulars	Govt respondents	Percentage	Pvt respondents	Percentage
WhatsApp Group	1	4.17	3	8.34
Personal contact	22	91.67	12	33.33
SMS	-	-	11	30.55
Customised App	-	-	4	11.11
Others	1	4.16	6	16.67
Total	24	100	36	100

***Multiple responses**

Primary Data

The above table reveals that in government school's majority 91.67% of the respondents update the parents through personal contact and only 4.16 % of the teachers update the parents through writing a dairy. In private school's majority 33.33% of the respondents update the parents through personal contact and only 8.34% of the respondents update the parents through WhatsApp group.

In both the school's parents are updated mostly through the personal contact but when compared, digital techniques are used more in private schools as to government schools for updating the parents.

Particulars	Govt respondents	Percentage	Pvt respondents	Percentage
Yes	18	72	21	84
No	1	4	-	-
Neutral	6	24	4	16
Total	25	100	25	100

Table no 9: Response towards digitalization results in better learning

Primary Data

The above table reveals, majority 72% of the government school respondents feels that digitalisation will result in better learning. Similarly, majority 84% of the private school respondents have a similar view as that of the government teachers.

Table no 9.1: reasons towards digitalization leading to better learning

Particulars	Govt respondents	Percentage	Pvt respondents	Percentage
Easy learning	15	60	8	25.81
Time saving	-	-	4	12.90
Interesting	10	40	19	61.29
Total	25	100	31	100

***Multiple responses**

Primary Data

The above table reveals, majority 60% of the government respondents feel that digitalization leads to easy learning and remaining 40% feel that it is an interesting way of learning. Whereas, Majority 61.29% of the respondents of private schools have perceived that it is an interesting mode of learning and only 12.90% of them feel that it saves their time.

Particulars	Govt respondents	Percentage	Pvt respondents	Percentage
Yes	21	84	25	100
No	4	16	-	-
Total	25	100	25	100

Table no 10: Response towards necessity of digitalization in today's competitive world

Primary Data

The above table reveals that majority 84% of the government respondents perceive that digitalization is necessary in today's competitive world. Similarly, cent percent of the private respondents have a similar opinion.

Hypothesis testing -2

Response of government school and private school teachers towards the perception that digitalisation is necessary in today's competitive world.

Table 10.1

Perception	Govt teachers	Private teachers	Total
Yes	21	25	46
No	4	-	4
Total	25	25	50

Primary Data

H0: No difference between the government and private school teachers about the perception that digitalisation is necessary in today's competitive world.

H1: There is difference between the government and private school teachers about the perception that digitalisation is necessary in today's competitive world.

Chi square test:

Row total for the row of that cell X Column total for the Column of that cell

$$\text{Expected frequency of any cell} = \frac{\text{-----}}{\text{Grand total}}$$

Table 10.2 Expected frequencies or Expected values

Perception	Govt teachers	Private teachers	Total
Yes	23	23	46
No	2	2	4
Total	25	25	50

Primary Data

Table 10.3: Calculation of Chi square

Observed frequency	Expected frequency	(O-E) ² /E
21	23	0.174
4	2	2
25	23	0.174
0	2	2
		4.348

Primary Data

$$X^2 = \sum[(O-E)^2/E] = 4.348$$

$$V = (r-1)(c-1) = (2-1)(2-1) = 1$$

For V = 1: Table value of Chi square at 5% level of significance = 3.841

Since the calculated value of Chi square is more than the Table value of Chi square, the null hypothesis is rejected and alternative hypothesis is accepted. **We therefore conclude that there is significance difference between the government and private school teachers about the perception that digitalisation is necessary in today's competitive world.**

Particulars	Govt respondents	Percentage	Pvt respondents	Percentage
Yes	15	60	14	56
No	6	24	10	40
Neutral	4	16	1	4
Total	25	100	25	100

Table no 11: Response towards popularity of schools based on usage digital methods

Primary Data

The above table reveals, majority 60% of the government school teachers have an opinion that schools using digital classes are popular than the once not using it and majority 56% of the private school respondents have a similar opinion. This shows that the government school teachers have a strong opinion on the above statement when compared to that of private teachers.

Table no 12: Response towards the statement "Technology never replace great teachers but technology in the hands of the great teachers is transformational."

Particulars	Govt respondents	Percentage	Pvt respondents	Percentage
Strongly Agree	12	48	8	32
Agree	12	48	16	64
Neutral	1	4	-	-
Disagree	-	-	1	4
Strongly disagree	-	-	-	-
Total	25	100	25	100

Primary Data

The above table reveals that majority of 48% of government school teachers strongly agree and agree the above statement respectively. Where as the majority 64% of the private teachers agree with the above statement.

5. FINDINGS

- In the government school's majority (56%) of them use the modern techniques in teaching and in the private school's majority (92%) of the teachers are inclined towards the modern teaching methods. The hypothesis testing concluded that there is significance difference between the government and private school teachers in using digital technology.
- In government school's out of the respondents who do not use digitalisation majority (57.9%) do not use as it is not mandatory. Similarly, out of the 3 private school responses majority (66.67%) of them have restricted to traditional methods of teaching.
- In the government school's majority (91.67%) of the teachers are not trained in using digital techniques and in contrast majority (88%) of the private school teachers are trained for using the same.
- In government school's majority (91.67%) of the respondents update the parents through personal contact. In private school's majority (33.33%) of the respondents

update the parents through personal contact and only (8.34%) of the respondents update the parents through WhatsApp group. Digital methods are you used in a higher rate in private schools as compared to that of government schools on updating the parents on the student's status.

- Majority 72% of the government school respondents feels that digitalisation will result in better learning. Similarly, majority 84% of the private school respondents have a similar view as that of the government teachers.
- Majority (84%) of the government respondents perceive that digitalization is necessary in today's competitive world. Similarly, cent percent of the private respondents have a similar opinion. The hypothesis testing concluded that there is significance difference between the government and private school teachers about the perception that digitalisation is necessary in today's competitive world.
- Majority 60% of the government school teachers have an opinion that schools using digital classes are popular than the once not using it and majority 56% of the private school respondents have a similar opinion
- Majority (48%) of government school teachers strongly agree and agree the statement "Technology never replace great teachers but technology in the hands of the great teachers is transformational." respectively. Whereas the majority (64%) of the private teachers agree with the above statement

6. SUGGESTIONS

- Lack of infrastructure in the government schools is discouraging the parents to admits their children to the government schools. So, the government should provide proper infrastructure facilities in order to attract the parents to admit their children.
- Digital education must be made mandatory in all the schools from the primary level because it is necessary for fostering the student's life and make them ready to face the competitive world.
- Along with making digital education compulsory all the facilities required to implement the digitalization should be given.
- In government schools there should one teacher for every class so that teachers can properly concentrate on each student and this will ease them in implementing digital techniques.
- Training must be provided on a continuous basis as the technology gets outdated rapidly. So, the teachers must have the knowledge of all recent digital technologies.

7. CONCLUSION

"The only constant thing is change so you have to learn to embrace it". Digital age is the truth of today lives which is unavoidable to live, learn and move ahead in today's world. Digitalization in education is a potentially liberating process helping the teachers and students in acquisition of information and enabling them to focus more on the creative processes of making connections and creating new paths. It offers great opportunities in education sector, especially to our schools as it provides information and learning. Existing traditional practices necessarily be changed by the use of technology in the future. Teachers must direct the students towards the right direction whereas students should be provided with the freedom to explore, discover and inquire. teachers must be provided with adequate training

and should be educated digitally. But all this will require support from our education system as well as the readiness to change and learn from everyone including the students.

8. REFERENCE

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